

SIRENE: A SOCIAL INNOVATION FRAMEWORK FOR REGIONAL INNOVATION AND ENTREPRENEURSHIP ECOSYSTEMS**Carina Dantas**

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Abstract

Purpose | SIRENE (Social Innovation Responsive Environments NETwork) is a European initiative supported by the Horizon Europe programme that aims to foster the growth of Regional Innovation and Entrepreneurship Ecosystems through social innovation, building their capacity to deliver eco-friendly and sustainable community-based services for Smart Healthy Age-Friendly Environments (SHAFE) implementation in Europe. To such aim, the consortium is developing a Social Innovation Framework for investment and the broad adoption of high-quality smart living solutions, combining key stakeholders, such as the housing sector and ICT infrastructure.

Methodology/Approach | The SIRENE framework aims to foster responsive, inclusive, and environmentally sustainable environments, encompassing both new constructions and renovations of existing housing to meet current societal needs. Targeting social entrepreneurs and innovation actors, it seeks to nurture ecosystems leading to innovative strategies for smart housing investments, particularly emphasizing independent and healthy living, while also advocating for environmentally conscious behaviors and sustainable practices, such as circular economy. The framework leverages on social innovation methodologies, blending an ecosystem approach with a quintuple-helix model involving citizens, policymakers, designers, builders, and housing providers from the private, public, or third sectors and recognizing the environment as a significant player in this ecosystem. The social innovation framework is being co-created with experts from all EU-27 countries and beyond, forming an Expert Hub for mutual collaboration and knowledge exchange. Besides this EU-wide Hub of Experts involved in iterative co-creation, SIRENE also features broader stakeholders' involvement through contributions and a voting procedure of the final framework including several online and presentational interactions, a set of large national events, and a European roadshow. In conclusion, SIRENE aims to empower local, regional and ecosystems within Europe by cultivating environments favourable to active and healthy living within an inclusive digital world. This methodology builds on sustained collaborative efforts among citizens, public authorities, industry stakeholders, NGOs, and research institutions, fostering a cohesive and dynamic partnership towards shared goals.

ABSTRACTS | 2024 APDR CONGRESS

Expected Results | Key components of the framework include: a) A guide for innovation actors outlining Social Innovation methodologies and concepts, with a focus on those promoting responsive, inclusive, and eco-friendly environments. b) A capacity-building framework tailored for social entrepreneurs, emphasizing funding opportunities and investment security. c) A practical toolkit comprising networking and learning exchange initiatives. d) A sustainability strategy featuring SHAFE business models and actionable ideas for innovative investments. e) A repository of best practices and Social Innovation initiatives in the SHAFE domain for benchmarking and future collaborations.

Keywords | Social Innovation – SHAFE – Network – Capacity-building – Co-creation.

References

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